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AND COPING EFFICACY

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The Relationships between Physical Activity and Athletes' Satisfaction: Mediating Role of Intrinsic Motivation and Coping Efficacy

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Abstract

This study investigates intricate relationships between physical activity and athletes' satisfaction, with a focus on mediating roles of coping efficacy and intrinsic motivation among the students in higher education institutions in Punjab, Pakistan. Physical activity is widely recognized as a crucial factor in promoting physical health and enhancing mental well-being, are crucial gears of athletes' overall satisfaction. However, mechanisms over which physical activity influences athletes' satisfaction remain underexplored, mainly in context of higher education in Pakistan. The research employs a survey methodology, targeting student-athletes from various universities and colleges

across Punjab. The study examines how regular engagement in physical activity contributes to athletes' satisfaction, not only through direct physical benefits but also by fostering intrinsic motivation and strengthening coping efficacy. Intrinsic motivation, defined as internal drive to participate in activities for inherent enjoyment and personal reward, is hypothesized to be significant mediator. The coping efficacy, is athlete's confidence in managing stressors and challenges associated with sports participation, is also explored as critical mediator. The ability to effectively cope with the demands of both academic and athletic responsibilities is essential for maintaining high levels of satisfaction. The study hypothesizes that athletes with high coping efficacy are more likely to experience greater satisfaction, as they are equipped to handle setbacks, pressure, competition-related stress. The findings of study are expected to offer valuable insights into the psychosocial factors that mediate relationship between physical activity and athletes' satisfaction the roles of intrinsic motivation and coping efficacy, the research aims to contribute to the development of targeted interventions that enhance sports experience for student-athletes in higher institutions. These findings will be mainly

relevant for coaches, psychologists, and educational administrators seeking to promote the athlete well-being and optimize performance in the context of Pakistani higher education.

Keywords: Physical Activity, Athletes' Satisfaction: Intrinsic Motivation, Coping Efficacy, Higher Education & Mediation

INTRODUCTION

Physical activity plays a central role in the lives of athletes, contributing not only to their physical fitness but also influencing various aspects of their psychological well-being. Athlete satisfaction is a multidimensional construct that encompasses their contentment, enjoyment, and fulfillment derived from participating in sports [1]. Understanding intricate relationship between physical activity and athletes' satisfaction is vital for optimizing performance, promoting mental health, and fostering a positive sporting experience [2]. Physical activity has been consistently linked to psychological well-being as engaging in regular exercise is linked with reduced stress, anxiety, and depression, and it contributes to improved moods and cognitive functions [3]. For athletes, whose physical activity is often intense and structured, psychological benefits can be extended intrinsic motivation refers to engaging in an activity for the inherent satisfaction and enjoyment it brings in lives.

In the context of sports, athletes driven by intrinsic motivation participate because they find the activity inherently rewarding. Understanding the role of intrinsic motivation is crucial as it may serve as a key factor influencing athletes' commitment, perseverance, and overall satisfaction with sporting experience [4]. The coping efficacy and belief in one's ability to effectively cope with challenges and adversities, is another vital psychological factor in sports as athletes encounter various stressors, like competition pressure, injuries, and performance expectations [5]. Coping efficacy plays a pivotal role in determining how athletes navigate these stressors, influencing their emotional well-being and overall satisfactions with their sports participations [6]. The athletes' satisfaction is a comprehensive measure encompassing various dimensions, including satisfaction with performance, team dynamics, coaching, and overall experience as required for chasing the diverse leading outcomes.

A satisfied athlete is likely to experience higher levels of motivation, commitment, and resilience, contributing to sustained engagement in the sports and improved performance. The relationship between physical activity and athletes' satisfaction is complex. While positive impact of physical activity on psychological well-being is well-established, specific mechanisms over which physical activity influences athletes' satisfaction need further exploration [7]. The intrinsic motivation and coping efficacy emerge as potential mediators, representing psychological pathways that

explain how engagement in physical activity pays to athletes' satisfaction [8]. Regular physical activity is a cornerstone of athletic training, contributing not only to physical health but also significantly affecting psychological well-being [9]. Athletes engage in strenuous activities that extend beyond mere exercise; their involvement is deeply intertwined with personal identity, team dynamics, and performance goals.

The intrinsic motivation, characterized by the internal drive to engage in an activity for inherent satisfaction it provides, is a crucial psychological factor in the athletic context. Athletes who are intrinsically motivated over sports participations [10]. This internal motivation led to sustained effort, persistence, and positive attitude toward training and competition. Athletes regularly face challenges, setbacks, and high-pressure situations as coping efficacy, or the belief in one's ability to effectively cope with stressors and challenges, becomes a determinant of an athlete's emotional well-being and performance [11]. The high coping efficacy is linked with adaptive stress responses, resilience, and the ability to navigate the demands of competitive sports effectively [12]. Athletes' satisfaction is a comprehensive construct of their sports experience. Satisfaction can be derived from performance achievements, positive team dynamic, effective coaching and overall enjoyment of sporting journey.

High levels of satisfaction are linked to enhanced motivation, commitment, and a sense of personal accomplishment. The relationship between physical activity and athletes' satisfaction is complex and multifaceted [13]. While physical activity contributes to overall well-being, understanding psychological mechanisms that mediate relationship is crucial as intrinsic motivation and coping efficacy emerge as potential mediators that can shed light on how engagement in physical activity influences athlete satisfaction [14]. The regular physical activity is fundamental for athlete health as it contributes to cardiovascular fitness, muscle strength, and physical well-being. Engaging in sports and exercise is linked to a lower risk of chronic diseases and promotes a healthy lifestyle [15]. Athletes' satisfaction is crucial for maintaining motivation and commitment to their sport. A satisfying fosters positive attitude, enjoyment, and sense of accomplishment, encouraging athletes to persevere over challenges.

The intrinsic motivation is a key driver for athletes to stay engaged in their sport. Athletes who find inherent satisfaction and enjoyment are more likely to commit to training, strive for personal improvement, and sustain long-term involvement in their chosen sport [16]. The coping efficacy is essential for athletes facing the inevitable challenges of sports. It influences an athlete's ability to cope with stress, setbacks, and high-pressure situations [17]. The interplay between physical activity, intrinsic motivation,

and coping efficacy can lead to optimal performance [18]. Athletes who physically active, intrinsically motivated, and possess effective coping strategies are better equipped to handle demands of competition and achieve peak performance. Intrinsic motivation coping efficacy contribute to athletes' well-being. Athletes with intrinsic motivation experience positive emotions related to their sport, while effective coping strategies help manage stress and maintain mental health.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The mediating roles of intrinsic motivation and coping efficacy in relationships between physical activity and athletes' satisfaction can offer valuable insights for optimizing athletic performance. Motivated and resilient athletes are likely to exhibit better performance outcomes. Mental health and satisfaction are closely linked, and strategies derived from this research can contribute to a positive athlete experience [22]. The coaches play central role in athlete development. Knowledge about the mediating factors in relationship between physical activity and satisfaction can guide coaches in adopting more effective coaching strategies [23]. This includes recognizing importance of motivation and coping skills in athlete development contribute to strategies that foster long-term engagement in sports [24]. Athletes who derive satisfaction from their activities, supported by intrinsic motivation and effective coping strategies, are likely to continue involvement in sports throughout their lives.

Intrinsic motivation and coping efficacy are closely related to positive mental health outcomes as recognizing the mediating roles of these factors can guide development of mental health support programs for athletes. The strategies can be implemented to enhance coping skills and address motivation factors that impact overall well-being [25]. Team dynamics significantly contribute to athletes' satisfaction. Coaches and team leaders can utilize study's findings to build positive team environments [26]. Thus, fostering intrinsic motivation and coping efficacy within team enhance cohesion, teamwork, and satisfaction as recognizing the mediating roles of intrinsic motivation and coping efficacy allows for a personalized approach to athlete development [27]. The coaches and sports professionals tailor their interventions to individual athletes, considering their unique motivational factors & coping styles prevalent issue among athletes, linked to lack of satisfaction and excessive stress.

The sympathetic to relations amid physical activity, intrinsic motivation, athletes' satisfaction, and coping efficacy involves exploring how these factors influence and interconnect one another within the context of physical activity and sports [10]. Any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure. For athletes, physical activity is structured more and aimed at improving performance [14]. It is

central to their competitive and training success. It includes sports, exercise, and daily activities. The physical regular activity is linked to improved mental and physical health, reducing risks of enhancing mood, chronic diseases, and improving overall quality of life [19]. Satisfaction stem from various factors, including personal performance, team success, social support, coaching quality, and the overall sporting environment. A positive emotional response to an athlete's sports experience, reflecting enjoyment and fulfillment in their participation for success.

The internal drive to engage in an activity for the inherent enjoyment and satisfaction derived from activity itself, rather than for external rewards. Intrinsic motivation in athletes is influenced by factors like competence, autonomy, and relatedness [22]. The higher levels of physical activity often led to greater satisfaction due to the improved fitness, performance, and social interactions within sports [24]. When athletes feel in control of their activities, believe in their abilities, and feel connected to others, intrinsic motivation is enhanced. The belief in one's ability to effectively overcome and manage stressors, challenges, and adversities within sports context [27]. Athletes with high intrinsic motivation are likely to find satisfaction in their sports and sustain consistent physical activity levels, as their participation is driven by personal enjoyment rather than external pressures coping efficacy supports intrinsic motivation by enabling to manage challenges without losing internal drive.

This improves satisfaction as athletes feel more capable and in control. Athletes with high coping efficacy are better equipped to handle the pressures of setbacks, competition, and injuries, leading to reduced anxiety, better performance, and greater satisfaction [35]. Athletes with high intrinsic motivation are likely to engage in physical activity reliably, as they derive personal fulfillment and enjoyment [36]. The physical activity, especially when it leads to perfection in fitness and skills, enhances athletes' satisfaction as motivation fuels resilience and persistence, which are crucial for effective coping. Athletes who are motivated intrinsically are likely more to believe in their coping abilities and satisfied with their sports experience are confident in ability to cope with stressors, enhancing their performance and well-being [37]. Coaches, trainers, and sports psychologists can leverage these interrelationships to foster environments that indorse intrinsic motivation, support actual coping strategies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is quantitative in nature that aims to examine relationship in chasing the hypotheses and reaching conclusion. The positivism approach was used to chasing relationships among research variables (physical activity, life satisfaction, and motivation) of study. The research approach specifies the way through which data is collected from the respondents by

retrieving them to reach their answers about variables of research in order to reach required conclusion through justification towards desired outcomes. The population of interest in this research is students hailing from colleges in KP, Pakistan wherein 2680 students from colleges wherein a sample is drawn from population (348), has been extracted by using the sampling formula widely used in the social research studies. Thus, 348 questionnaires were distributed among which 340 were recollected and used for analysis. Similarly, the random simple technique was used to access the population of study which comes under the non-probability technique to ensure required data from diverse dimensions. Also, both secondary and primary data were used to collect data from respondents and from existing knowledge databased to analyze data to reach conclusion. The questionnaires were adopted from previous studies. Similarly, 5-point Likert scale was used to record responses of respondents about research issues in particular context to access respondents and achieving desired outcomes.

RESULTS OF STUDY

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Physical Activities	336	1.30	4.80	3.2142	.76720
Intrinsic Motivation	336	1.80	4.60	3.1709	.84420
Coping Efficacy	336	1.70	4.70	3.4563	.58882
Athletes' Satisfaction	336	1.63	4.62	3.3639	.60593
Valid N (listwise)	336				

The descriptive statistics provides the information about describing research variables in terms of sample, minimum and maximum response rates, mean and standard deviation of respondents' responses about research issues like sports participation, emotional intelligence, social support and cognitive abilities. The table provides significant values in reaching the decision about the description of variables as all the values are significant and as per the required threshold values about research issues.

H-No. 1 There is positive association between physical activity, intrinsic motivation, coping efficacy and athletes' satisfaction (H1).

Correlations Analysis

		[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
Physical Activities [1]	Pearson Correlation	1	.370**	.616**	.646**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	336	336	336	336
Intrinsic Motivation [2]	Pearson Correlation	.370**	1	.397**	.379**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	336	336	336	336
Coping Efficacy [3]	Pearson Correlation	.616**	.397**	1	.644**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	336	336	336	336
Athletes' Satisfaction [4]	Pearson Correlation	.646**	.379**	.644**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	336	336	336	336

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation procedure provides important outcomes about the association amid the research variables of current study like physical activity, intrinsic motivation, coping efficacy and athletes' satisfaction with respect to strength and direction in association among the research variables of current study. The results revealed that there is positive and significant and positive association among the research variables like physical activity and athletes' satisfaction ($R = .646$ & $P = 000$), physical activity and intrinsic motivation ($R = .370$ & $P = 000$), physical activity and coping efficacy ($R = .616$ & $P = 000$), intrinsic motivation and athletes' satisfaction ($R = .379$ & $P = 000$), coping efficacy and athletes' satisfaction ($R = .644$ & $P = 000$), and intrinsic motivation and coping efficacy ($R = .397$ & $P = 000$), and thus from correlation results, the hypothesis from results in thus accepted from correlation outcomes.

H-No. 2 There is positive impact of physical activity, intrinsic motivation, coping efficacy on athletes' satisfaction (H2).

Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	F	Std. Error of Estimate
1	.722a	.521	.517		.42113

Regression Analysis

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	64.115	3	21.372	120.503	.000b
	Residual	58.881	332	.177		
	Total	122.996	335			

Regression Analysis

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.862	.142		6.073	.000
	Physical Activities	.302	.039	.382	7.808	.000
	Intrinsic Motivation	.064	.030	.089	2.130	.034
	Coping Efficacy	.384	.051	.373	7.529	.000

a. Predictors: Physical Activities, Coping Efficacy & Intrinsic Motivation

b. Dependent Variable: Athletes' Satisfaction

The regression procedure was used to examine the impact of predicting variables likewise physical activity, intrinsic motivation, coping efficacy on dependent variable of study athletes' satisfaction in order to confirm the prediction. The results of regression revealed that there is 52.1% change in athletes' satisfaction is due to the physical activity, intrinsic motivation, coping efficacy with the significant impact like physical activity ($\beta = .302$ & P-value = .000), intrinsic motivation ($\beta = .064$ & P-value = .034), coping efficacy ($\beta = .384$ & P-value = .000), and thus hypothesis from the results is hence accepted.

H-No. 3 There is significant mediating role of intrinsic motivation in linking physical activity and athletes' satisfaction (H3).

First Mediation Steps (a)

Mediation Analysis (Model Summary) (H3)

R	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.3703	.1371	.6168	65.4945	1.0000	334.0000	.0000

Mediation Analysis (Coefficient) (H3)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.8612	.1546	12.0412	.0000	1.5571	2.1652
Physical Activities	.4075	.0504	8.0929	.0000	.3084	.5065

Predicting Variable: Physical Activities

Criterion Variable: Intrinsic Motivation

Second & Third Mediation Steps (b & c)

Mediation Analysis (Model Summary) (H3)

R	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6630	.4395	.2070	143.3106	2.0000	333.0000	.0000

Mediation Analysis (Coefficient) (H3)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.5081	.1221	12.3512	.0000	1.2679	1.7483
Intrinsic Motivation	.1166	.0329	3.5389	.0005	.0518	.1814
Physical Activities	.4624	.0342	13.5323	.0000	.3952	.5296

Predicting Variable: Physical Activities & Intrinsic Motivation

Criterion Variable: Athletes' Satisfaction

Fourth Mediation Step (c)

Mediation Analysis (Model Summary) (H3)

R	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6456	.4168	.2148	256.2959	1.0000	334.0000	.0000

Mediation Analysis (Coefficient) (H3)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.7251	.1096	15.7355	.0000	1.5094	1.9407
Physical Activities	.5099	.0318	16.0092	.0000	.4472	.5725

Independent Variable: Physical Activities

Dependent Variable: Athletes' Satisfaction

The mediation procedure was used to examine the mediating role of intrinsic motivation to link the physical activities and athletes' satisfaction through four paths conditional mediation process in order to confirm the mediation that whether it is partial mediation of full mediation. The results revealed the information about first path wherein 13.71% variance occurred in intrinsic motivation is due to physical activities with significant impact ($\beta = .4075$ & P-value = .0000). The second and third path revealed the information about the indirect relationship wherein 43.95% variance has been occurred in athletes' satisfaction is due to intrinsic motivation and physical activities with significant impact like intrinsic motivation ($\beta = .1166$ & P-value = .0005), and physical activities ($\beta = .4624$ & P-value = .0000), that provides the clues towards the fourth mediation path towards the direct relationship.

DISCUSSION

Physical activity plays a central role in the lives of athletes, contributing not only to their physical fitness but also influencing various aspects of their psychological well-being. Athlete satisfaction is a multidimensional

construct that encompasses their contentment, enjoyment, and fulfillment derived from participating in sports [1]. Understanding intricate relationship between physical activity and athletes' satisfaction is vital for optimizing performance, promoting mental health, and fostering a positive sporting experience [2]. Physical activity has been consistently linked to psychological well-being as engaging in regular exercise is linked with reduced stress, anxiety, and depression, and it contributes to improved moods and cognitive functions [3]. For athletes, whose physical activity is often intense and structured, psychological benefits can be extended intrinsic motivation refers to engaging in an activity for the inherent satisfaction and enjoyment it brings in lives.

The intrinsic motivation is a key driver for athletes to stay engaged in their sport. Athletes who find inherent satisfaction and enjoyment are more likely to commit to training, strive for personal improvement, and sustain long-term involvement in their chosen sport [16]. The coping efficacy is essential for athletes facing the inevitable challenges of sports. It influences an athlete's ability to cope with stress, setbacks, and high-pressure situations [17]. The interplay between physical activity, intrinsic motivation, and coping efficacy can lead to optimal performance [18]. Athletes who physically active, intrinsically motivated, and possess effective coping strategies are better equipped to handle demands of competition and achieve peak performance. Intrinsic motivation coping efficacy contribute to athletes' well-being. Athletes with intrinsic motivation experience positive emotions related to their sport, while effective coping strategies help manage stress and maintain mental health.

The internal drive to engage in an activity for the inherent enjoyment and satisfaction derived from activity itself, rather than for external rewards. Intrinsic motivation in athletes is influenced by factors like competence, autonomy, and relatedness [22]. The higher levels of physical activity often led to greater satisfaction due to the improved fitness, performance, and social interactions within sports [24]. When athletes feel in control of their activities, believe in their abilities, and feel connected to others, intrinsic motivation is enhanced. The belief in one's ability to effectively overcome and manage stressors, challenges, and adversities within sports context [27]. Athletes with high intrinsic motivation are likely to find satisfaction in their sports and sustain consistent physical activity levels, as their participation is driven by personal enjoyment rather than external pressures coping efficacy supports intrinsic motivation by enabling to manage challenges without losing internal drive.

The enhanced coping efficacy supports effective and consistent physical activity, which is crucial for athletic performance and development. The quality and outcomes of physical activity influence directly athletes'

satisfaction. Intrinsic motivation is significant predictor of athletes' satisfaction [41]. Athletes who are driven by internal rewards like mastery, enjoyment, and personal growth are likely to experience satisfaction from sports involvement [42]. When physical activity results in positive outcomes like physical fitness, improved performance, and social interactions, athletes are more likely to feel satisfied with their sports experience. Satisfaction from physical activity reinforces desire to continue participating, creating a positive cycle of engagement and fulfillment [43]. Effective coping enhances athletes' satisfaction by enabling them to navigate the challenges of their sport successfully. Athletes with coping efficacy adversity without becoming discouraged with the exhaustion.

Recommendations

1. There is a need to encourage athletes to set meaningful and personal goals that align with their intrinsic values and interests to focus from external rewards to personal satisfaction and diverse achievements.
2. To create an environment that supports the athletes' autonomy by allowing them to make choices about their rivalry and training strategies sense control and personal investment in their diverse activities.
3. Implement stress management techniques such as relaxation exercises, mindfulness, and visualization to enhance athletes' coping efficacy manage pressures and stresses associated with competitive sports.
4. To provide training focused on building psychological resilience, including techniques for sustaining positive mindset and handling setbacks athlete ability to cope with challenges and recover from failures.
5. To develop strong support systems, including access to sports psychologists, mentors, and peer support networks, to provide the athletes with additional resources for coping with stress and adversity.

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